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The UN80 Initiative as a Productive Failure: Between Geopolitical Disruptions and Organizational Path Dependency

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Contents

ABSTRACT	4
1. INTRODUCTION	5
2. OUTLINE OF THIS CONTRIBUTION AND KEY MESSAGES	6
3. ACADEMIC PERSPECTIVES ON UN REFORM AND THE UN80 PROCESS(ES)	9
NON-REFORM IN INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS (IOs): A COMPARATIVE PERSPECTIVE	10
REFORMING UNDER FINANCIAL PRESSURES ('WORKSTREAM 1')	11
POLICY ACCUMULATION AND THE PATHOLOGIES OF THE UN MANDATE REVIEW ('WORKSTREAM 2')	12
REFORMING THE COMPLEX UN SYSTEM AND THE JOINT DECISION-TRAP ('WORKSTREAM 3')	13
4. THE UN80 INITIATIVE IN THE FIRST HALF OF 2025: FROM SHOCK, TO CONFUSION, TO A STRUCTURED APPROACH	15
5. ASSESSING THE THREE WORKSTREAMS OF UN80	20
5.1 'WORKSTREAM 1': BUDGET CUTS WITH LIMITED EFFICIENCY GAINS	20
5.2 ASSESSING 'WORKSTREAM 2': A CREATIVE PROCESS WITH UNCLEAR RESULTS	21
5.3 ASSESSING 'WORKSTREAM 3': A LONG TO-DO LIST, WITH MORE ACTION THAN PLAN	23
6. UN80 AND THE IGNORANCE OF GEOPOLITICAL DISRUPTIONS	26
7. SHORT CONCLUSIONS AND OUTLOOK BEYOND 2026	28
8. RECOMMENDATIONS	29
REFERENCES	31

THE UN80 INITIATIVE AS A PRODUCTIVE FAILURE: BETWEEN GEOPOLITICAL DISRUPTIONS AND ORGANIZATIONAL PATH DEPENDENCY

Ronny Patz

Abstract

In March 2025, UN Secretary-General Antonio Guterres initiated the UN80 reform initiative. Organized around three ‘workstreams’, the UN80 initiative combined very ambitious reform and restructuring goals with extremely tight timelines under massive resource constraints. The workstreams combined budget cuts announced as efficiency gains and internal reorganization (Workstream 1). They included a UN decision-making reform announced initially as a mandate review (Workstream 2) and proposals for reform(s) of the entire UN system structure (Workstream 3) that ended up with relatively limited, disconnected, and uncoordinated proposals for mergers and joint services. At the start of 2026, the UN80 reform process is ongoing and on a path to a productive failure. Failure, first, because ambition and financial crisis clashed and, second, because member states’ interests and geopolitical realities were not openly factored in. UN80 nevertheless succeeded in putting large-scale reform on the agenda and in linking up disconnected smaller reform efforts under a common roof. This GGI Analysis¹ situates this critical appraisal in the literature on international organization reform and policy accumulation. It provides recommendations on how to better balance bureaucratic, diplomatic, geofiscal, and geopolitical aspects of reform dynamics in times of (budget) crisis, acknowledging that a fundamental system-wide reform is almost impossible from within the current global governance complex.

¹ This analysis was drafted during December 2025 and January 2026. The initial editorial deadline after which no new information was included was 31 January 2026.

1. Introduction

“Let me say all of this with a reality check: this is a fast-moving process. The Secretary-General said at the last meeting of the [UN80] steering committee that took place last week that [...] he wants to see, in the remainder of his mandate, move [everything] very quickly forward. He wants, by High-Level Week next year, to have very substantial progress ‘across the waterfront’, as it were, of the UN80 Initiative [...]”

USG Guy Ryder, key UN80 reform manager (15 Dec. 2025)²

In July 2025, this author suggested in the GGI Policy Paper **“Reforming the United Nations during a Financial Crisis”**³ that combining massive cutback management in the largest financial crunch in recent UN history with strategic efforts for a major UN system reform would be extremely challenging. As 2025 has come to an end, this contribution expands on this theme and explores to what degree earlier predictions could be confirmed, what role different actors have played along different timelines, and where the UN reform(s) and cutback(s) are heading in 2026 and beyond.

The pace and scope at which the UN80 initiative has progressed in less than one year are both breathtaking and confusing. Generally, ‘breathtaking’ or ‘confusing’ are not the first adjectives that come to mind for describing a *successful* reform process. This initiative that was started by UN Secretary-General Antonio Guterres in March 2025 is also not a single process. It is a multitude of partially interlinked and fast-tracked UN reform ideas, many predating 2025. While combined under the roof of UN80, these ideas did not converge to an overall vision for the future of a functioning UN system. In a year when geopolitics developed with breathtaking speed, UN80 added to an overall confusing global context instead of helping to stabilize the situation of global multilateralism.

The Secretary-General’s own urgency, and the lack of a substantive reform coordination among member states during the first half of 2025, all this under conditions of political uncertainty and massive cuts, generated anxiety and coordination problems. In the absence of predictable funding, UN staff, diplomats, and the wider policy community found it difficult to disentangle cost-cutting from actual reform measures, short-term stabilization from system reorganization.

² Global AI Center | POLINA PRIANYKOVA | UN80 Briefing by Under-Secretary-General Guy Ryder; <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=kukCR2St5Xs&t=313s>.

³ Patz, Ronny (2025). "Reforming the UN During a Financial Crisis: A Foreseeable Failure to Align

Money, Mandates and Majorities." Global Governance Institute.

<https://www.globalgovernance.eu/publications/reforming-the-un-during-a-financial-crisis-a-foreseeable-failure-to-align-money-mandates-and-majorities>.

The lack of a convincing communication strategy by the UN80 reform leadership made it even harder to develop a credible reform narrative behind which many relevant actors could unite, especially when parts of the agenda were driven by Trump's attempts to undermine global multilateralism, not good-faith reform. UN80 meant something different for everyone involved, and little significant progress was reached at system level by early 2026 beyond massive staff cuts that were necessary due to a lack of funding, not reform.

2. Outline of this contribution and key messages

The present analysis of the dynamics behind the UN80 process in 2025 builds on publicly available documents and recorded public meetings of the UN and key actors. Over the course of nine months (May 2025-January 2026), the author interacted with several dozen (present and former) UN officials and member state diplomats who have shared, in person, in writing, in Zoom calls, or via direct messages (on LinkedIn and other platforms) their insights, concerns, and expectations. A dedicated semi-public call to provide additional feedback made by the author in December 2025 was answered by additional UN officials from Geneva and

New York.⁴ The author has continuously documented the evolution of key steps of the crisis and the reforms and builds on this commentary.⁵ Many other UN80-related contributions have been published throughout the past year and inform the present contribution.

Based on these diverse perspectives, this contribution argues that the UN80 initiative can be described, overall, as a *productive failure* so far.

The process was *productive* because it channeled the response to the UN financial crisis into something bigger than just cutting down. It also succeeded in engaging the UN system at large, not just individual parts. It achieved to frame diverse ongoing reflection processes under a singular ambitious reform roof ('UN80'), which allowed actors to look at individual reform proposals in a wider context. These smaller and larger reform proposals may not have received the same level of attention that they received collectively under this UN80 roof and under the headlines of 'Workstream 1-3'. Finally, UN80 generated administrative and intergovernmental dynamics not seen in the collective UN system in a while. This included structured reflections on

⁴ Patz, Ronny. LinkedIn post requesting feedback. https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ronny-patz_unsystem-unitednations-activity-7406003792703287297-136L/.

⁵ Patz, Ronny (2025/26). "The United Nations' financial crisis & UN80 reform", Polscieu blog. <https://polscieu.wordpress.com/2025/06/24/the-united-nations-financial-crisis/>

downsizing the entire UN system⁶ and it resulted in the most substantive UN Regular Budget cuts in decades,⁷ which were sold as efficiency gains under Workstream 1. The creation of an intergovernmental UN80 working group that engaged member states much more creatively than some previous discussions provided insights on how to organize future reforms better.⁸ Altogether, the UN80 process offered platforms for diverse reform discussions among UN experts, within the UN's administrative leadership, and among member states, even generating some radical proposals from inside the UN system.⁹ This can set the tone for the reforms of global multilateralism that will be necessary for the emerging new global order.

At the same time, **the process can be seen as a failure** because there is no indication that, even if the Action Plan¹⁰ presented by the UN Secretary-General in November 2025 were to be implemented in full, the UN system

would be fit for purpose. Reform proposals started large but returned to *status quo*-oriented discussions, for example on mergers. Procedurally, the initiative failed because Guterres put administrative initiative and bureaucratic restructuring before political initiative and intergovernmental realignment.¹¹ It failed in communications because it sold necessary *ad hoc* cutback management in a deep financial crisis as structural reforms instead of separating the two more clearly.¹² Ultimately, major reform ideas and the search for a more coherent UN system got lost in budgetary micromanagement under excessively short timelines.¹³ UN80 thus created the expectations of a major reform process, but the rushed timeline in the first half of 2025 did not allow the process to settle on a clear path. Time and creative freedom were only taken in the “discovery phase” of the member state working group on UN80. The impression was that Secretary-General Guterres wanted to

⁶ UN System Staff College (UNSSC). "Downsizing in the United Nations: Managing impact, building resilience, and seizing strategic opportunity" October 2025. https://www.unssc.org/sites/default/files/node/resources/field_resource/2025-10/Downsizing%20in%20the%20United%20Nations%20-%20FINAL_0.pdf.

⁷ United Nations. "General Assembly Approves \$3.45 Billion Regular Budget for 2026." <https://www.un.org/en/delegate/general-assembly-approves-345-billion-regular-budget-2026>.

⁸ United Nations (UN80 Initiative). "Informal Ad Hoc Working Group – Member State Inputs." <https://www.un.org/un80-initiative/en/informal-ad-hoc-working-group-member-state-inputs>.

⁹ United Nations (UN80 Task Force). "UN80 structural changes and programmatic realignment Compilation of non-attributable suggestions by the UN80 Task Force". April 2025. Leaked document published by Health Policy Watch. [https://healthpolicy-watch.news/wp-](https://healthpolicy-watch.news/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/Consolidated_ideas_realignments_restricted_2504081.pdf)

[content/uploads/2025/05/Consolidated_ideas_realignments_restricted_2504081.pdf](https://www.un.org/un80-actions).

¹⁰ See the UN80 Action Plan Dashboard: <https://un80actions.un.org>.

¹¹ Camelli, Thibault. "UN80 Enters Its Political Phase: What Member States Must Do Now to Own It." IPI Global Observatory, 15 December 2025. <https://theglobalobservatory.org/2025/12/un80-enters-its-political-phase-what-member-states-must-do-now-to-own-it/>.

¹² Multilateral Organisation Performance Assessment Network (MOPAN). "Multilateral effectiveness in a shifting landscape. Mapping of multilateral organisations' response to the current funding environment." December 2025. <https://www.mopan.org/content/dam/mopan/en/publications/our-work/insights/thematic-briefs/mapping/mopan-mapping-exercise-2025.pdf>.

¹³ Camelli, Thibault (2025). "How to Make Sense of the ACABQ Report on UN80." Center on International Cooperation, NYU. <https://cic.nyu.edu/resources/how-to-make-sense-of-the-acabq-report-on-un80/>.

make UN80 his legacy and pushed through proposals for which there was little intergovernmental or UN system appetite, favoring superficial wins and ignoring failure. At the beginning of 2026, it is also clear that geopolitical events are overtaking the reforms because UN80 lacks a clear governance reform track, ignoring that failed implementation and systemic fragmentation are features of decision-making much more than of bureaucratic structures. The key feature of the failure of UN80, therefore, is that cost-cutting efforts have changed the UN system much more in 2025 than any of the formal reform proposals for UN80. It will be on the next Secretary-General(s) to see if they can take up some of the dynamics and turn them into future successes.

While this critical appraisal as “productive failure” reflects the gap between communicated ambitions, structural conditions, and actual outcomes, academic research on (non-)reform of international organizations as well as on policy accumulation and triage suggests that such a failure was indeed the most likely outcome (see discussions below) – so maybe a *productive* failure was the best possible outcome.

The key question is what one can learn from the experiences in 2025 heading into 2026-28, knowing that major leaders have indicated in recent speeches that the old global order is

over.¹⁴ Especially member states, small and large, as the collective principal of the UN, and as donors for the operational work of the UN,¹⁵ will need to step up their collective action to overcome the pathologies of UN reform, while a new Secretary-General will need to capitalize on the first year in office to catalyze such collective action. It is too easy to blame the failure(s) of UN80 on the UN Secretary-General, when it took member states until early 2026 to openly admit that something bigger than UN80 needed to be done.

This paper will thus formulate six key recommendations, which combined suggest that a new Secretary-General should use their political capital to initiate an honest assessment of the state of the UN system in early 2027, using the analytical capacities of think tanks, academia, and the UN system itself, to help transition from UN80’s managerial approach to a big-picture political process that creates the conditions for collective and as-joint-as-possible action among member states. The goal should be to rethink the wider UN system from a bird’s-eye perspective, recognizing the divergent interests of major, middle- and minor powers in the new world order and to acknowledge where the UN system just serves the interests of a few, well-meaning or not.

¹⁴ World Economic Forum. "Davos 2026: Special Address by Mark Carney, Prime Minister of Canada." 20 January 2026. <https://www.weforum.org/stories/2026/01/davos->

[2026-special-address-by-mark-carney-prime-minister-of-canada/](https://www.weforum.org/stories/2026/01/davos-2026-special-address-by-mark-carney-prime-minister-of-canada/).

¹⁵ For an overview on the UN’s operational system: <https://www.understandingtheun.org/documents/UN-Country-Level-handbook.pdf>.

3. Academic perspectives on UN reform and the UN80 process(es)

To situate the structural reform impulses of UN80 and the parallel UN system financial crisis in ongoing academic debates, one might start with the observation that these impulses are symptoms of and responses to the crisis of the “Liberal International Order”, a crisis that has been announced for years and now is officially there.¹⁶ UN80 was a first response of UN bureaucrats to the US’ and other member states’ increasing contestation of the organizational setup of the current order¹⁷, attempting to help reorganize the current global multilateral governance and regime complexity without addressing the root causes.¹⁸

It is, however, not the main aim of this contribution to dive deeply into the change of global order, but rather to follow more closely where UN80 was heading and why it has failed productively. UN80 will be situated in a narrower set of key academic debates

of the past decade focused on global governance reform, including in times of crisis.

The baseline assumption for reform in international organizations (IOs) following from these literatures is **path dependence** in the form of either quick and gradual formal change or slow, “subterranean” informal and formal transformations over extended time periods.¹⁹ Successful large-scale reform processes are only possible quickly when reformers control both money and majorities.²⁰ This rarely coincides in institutions like the UN where voting is dominated by one-country-one-vote. Where everyone is equal in collective decisions while funding is dominated by a few major contributors, assessed or voluntary, the divergence between vote-based and money-based reform coalitions is often too large. The path-dependent institutional change of global institutions is therefore only rarely interrupted by punctuated changes. Even major political or economic shocks may ultimately be translated into slow-moving reform processes.²¹ Thus, while this contribution describes UN80 as an expected (productive) failure, the question for the future becomes how vote-based and funding-

¹⁶ Ikenberry, G. John. "The end of liberal international order?." *International affairs* 94, no. 1 (2018): 7-23.

¹⁷ Heinkelmann-Wild, Tim, and Vytautas Jankauskas. "To yield or shield? Comparing international public administrations' responses to member states' policy contestation." *Journal of Comparative Policy Analysis: Research and Practice* 24, no. 3 (2022): 296-312.

¹⁸ Alter, Karen J. "The promise and perils of theorizing international regime complexity in an evolving world." *The Review of International Organizations* 17, no. 2 (2022): 375-396.

¹⁹ Graham, Erin R. *Transforming International Institutions: How money quietly sidelined multilateralism at the United Nations*. Oxford University Press, 2023.

²⁰ Hanrieder, Tine. "Gradual change in international organisations: Agency theory and historical institutionalism." *Politics* 34, no. 4 (2014): 324-333.

²¹ Rixen, Thomas, Lora Anne Viola, and Michael Zürn, eds. *Historical institutionalism and international relations: Explaining institutional development in world politics*. Oxford University Press, 2016.

based reform decisions can be aligned within and across UN agencies and what temporal sequencing and pacing may increase the chances of larger-scale reforms, including at system-level.

Non-reform in international organizations (IOs): a comparative perspective

Recent academic contributions on a range of international institutions, including in the UN system, have shown that both the demand and the geopolitical context of reforming IOs are changing. Instead of major *policy* reform, the trend is towards internal reforms that “maneuver around gridlock”.²² Large-scale comparative academic studies with a focus on administrative (non-)reforms across many UN agencies are rare. Reform-oriented case studies tend to focus on individual UN agencies.²³ One of the few larger comparative studies covering 11 international agencies – including in FAO, ILO, IOM, and the World Bank – showed that agencies that have different administrative styles – e.g., more servant or more entrepreneurial bureaucracies – tend to choose different reform paths with

different aims between Weberian and New Public Management style administration.²⁴ Comparing attempts to structurally reform UN Specialized Agencies (WHO, UNESCO, ILO), especially attempts to reduce fragmentation *within* these agencies, suggested that fragmentation can be built into the DNA of UN agencies so that many reform efforts increase fragmentation instead of reducing it.²⁵ This tendency is the result of budgetary procedures where segmentation and fragmentation are seen as solutions to division among member states and major geopolitical blocs.²⁶

For UN reform at agency-level, this suggests that reforming against established organizational structures is difficult, especially when those structures represent fiefdoms of (bloc of) member states.²⁷ Where reforms try to achieve more efficiency and effectiveness across an entire system of individual agencies, this suggests that while different agency bureaucracies may respond differently to reform proposals, similar constellations of member states across assemblies and governing boards could result in similar (non-)results. In this sense, the impetus of UN80 to trigger system-wide reforms seemed right but needed to take account of the

²² Hylke Dijkstra. 2026. “Reforming Global Institutions in an Era of Geopolitical Strain: Evidence from 15 Case Studies.” ENSURED Research Report, no. 24 (January): 1-30.

<https://www.ensuredeurope.eu>; p.6.

²³ Hemmerich, Katja. “Assessing the Ability of the UN80 Action Plan to Effect Real Change.” ReformWorks, 9 November 2025.

<https://www.reformworks.org/post/assessing-the-ability-of-the-un80-action-plan-to-effect-real-change>.

²⁴ Grohs, Stephan, and Daniel Rasch. “Administrative convergence in the United Nations system?”

Patterns of administrative reform in four United Nations organizations over time.” *International Review of Administrative Sciences* 87, no. 4 (2021): 755-774.

²⁵ Hanrieder, Tine. *International organization in time: Fragmentation and reform*. OUP Oxford, 2015.

²⁶ Patz, Ronny, and Klaus H. Goetz. *Managing money and discord in the UN: Budgeting and bureaucracy*. Oxford University Press, 2019.

²⁷ Kleine, Mareike. “Trading control: national fiefdoms in international organizations.” *International Theory* 5, no. 3 (2013): 321-346.

different constellations of administrative and member state actors and power centers to trigger successful reform dynamics.²⁸

Reforming under financial pressures ('Workstream 1')

In the paper "*Reforming the UN during a financial crisis: a foreseeable failure to align money, mandates, and majorities?*"²⁹, this author argued that reforming international agencies was already difficult in normal times, whatever 'normal' means in the international system, but that it was even harder when UN agencies were faced with massive cuts at the same time.

A key finding in the literature has been that, during financial crises, there can be a fundamental temporal disconnect between UN administrative realization of the impacts of a resource crisis and the ability or willingness of member states to realize that political decisions, notably on policy prioritization, have to be taken in order to respond. Thus,

administrative reform efforts will most likely precede intergovernmental reform efforts. By the time member states are willing to act, the UN's administration can already be so cut down and reform-fatigued that member states' decisions will hit limited bureaucratic enthusiasm or energy for further actions.³⁰

At the same time, times of existential crisis trigger "IO survival politics" where senior leaders of international organizations will try extraordinary measures, rhetorically, strategically, and in terms of policy proposals to ensure their organization's survival against external or internal threats.³¹ There is also a tendency to centralize decision-making in times of budgetary crisis.³² However, as the formal constraints for senior IO leaders differ across international organizations, their entrepreneurship can be severely limited. As a result, even the most creative attempts may end up looking like muddling through, especially when key veto players prevent major reforms in times of crisis.³³

²⁸ Schönrock, Philipp, Frederik Matthys, Arellys Bellorini, and Anna Novoselova (2026). "The Triple Disconnect. Power, Money, and Voice in the UN Development System: mapping influence and informality"; Cepei, available at: <https://cepei.org/wp-content/uploads/2026/02/Power-Money-and-Voice-in-the-UN-Development-System-Report.pdf>.

²⁹ Patz, Ronny (2025). "Reforming the UN During a Financial Crisis: A Foreseeable Failure to Align Money, Mandates and Majorities." Global Governance Institute. <https://www.globalgovernance.eu/publications/reforming-the-un-during-a-financial-crisis-a-foreseeable-failure-to-align-money-mandates-and-majorities>.

³⁰ Eckhard, Steffen, Ronny Patz, and Sylvia Schmidt. "Reform efforts, synchronization failure, and international bureaucracy: the case of the UNESCO

budget crisis." *Journal of European Public Policy* 26, no. 11 (2019): 1639-1656.

³¹ Schuette, Leonard August. "IO survival politics: international organisations amid the crisis of multilateralism." *Journal of European Public Policy* 31, no. 11 (2024): 3812-3838.

³² Patz, Ronny, and Klaus H. Goetz. "Changing budgeting administration in international organizations: budgetary pressures, complex principals and administrative leadership." In *International bureaucracy: Challenges and lessons for public administration research*, pp. 123-150. London: Palgrave Macmillan UK, 2016.

³³ Friesendorf, Cornelius, and Ronny Patz. "International Bureaucracies as Constrained Entrepreneurs: The Budget Crisis of the OSCE." *Global Policy* (2025).

A key expectation for the efficiency agenda and cutback agenda under Workstream 1 would have been that a push by the UN Secretary-General to cut down the organization would not have been followed by member states, first because they would not see the same pressure as the UN's executive leadership, and second because they might not have liked the ideas put forward by the Secretary-General. The adoption of the reduced UN regular budget at the end of 2025 was thus more surprising than expected.

Policy accumulation and the pathologies of the UN mandate review ('Workstream 2')

Very little UN-focused research is available on the mandate lifecycle dimension, one of the three angles of the UN80 initiative ('Workstream 2').³⁴ In essence, this is a debate on the accumulation and duplication of mandates within and across UN entities. It also includes questions of fragmentation (different UN entities covering similar mandates) and centralization (which entity should be in the lead). One key topic addressed is the inability of the UN system to sunset old, outdated, superseded, or contradictory mandates. The results are competition between agencies, thinly

financed micro-mandates, extensive and overlapping reporting obligations, new mandates that are layered on top of old mandates without new resources, or uncoordinated work of different agencies on the same topics. While part of the problem is the complexity and overlap within the wider UN system, which is addressed in the third workstream of UN80 (see below), a central topic became whether the creation of new mandates could be limited or outdated and marginalized mandates could be abolished.

The UN system treated these dynamics as a particular UN problem. However, the challenges of "policy accumulation" have been identified as a key problem of present-day public policy-making well beyond the global level.³⁵ The results of policy accumulation are overloaded public bureaucracies and, ultimately, the need to prioritize policies (= mandates) by available time, resources, or political mood, leading to policy "triage", not by formally abandoning policies.³⁶ In the core UN, new mandates often have to be implemented "within existing resources", which is exactly the kind of policy-making that forces the UN administration to either make triage choices (= prioritize resources for one policy over the other) or to fulfil many mandates so thinly that none of them

³⁴ United Nations. "Mandate Implementation Review". Report of the Secretary General on Workstream 2 of the UN80 Initiative. September 2025. https://www.un.org/un80-initiative/sites/default/files/2025-09/2512998E_MIR_web.pdf.

³⁵ Adam, Christian, Yves Steinebach, and Christoph Knill. "Neglected challenges to evidence-based

policy-making: The problem of policy accumulation." *Policy Sciences* 51, no. 3 (2018): 269-290.

³⁶ Knill, Christoph, Yves Steinebach, and Dionys Zink. "How policy growth affects policy implementation: bureaucratic overload and policy triage." *Journal of European Public Policy* 31, no. 2 (2024): 324-351.

are implemented as expected by member states.

A key argument of the academic policy accumulation literature is that there is a close link between overload, resources, and (implementation) performance. Translated to the global level, UN member states that do *not* care about implementation may also not care about a reduction in the policy burden of the UN Secretariat. Those states that care about UN performance and are unhappy about under-implementation ('ineffectiveness' or 'inefficiency') are not willing to provide additional resources to allow the UN to implement all mandates, even if under-implementation is the result of resource scarcity, leading to a cycle of efficiency cuts and increasing underperformance. In addition, when states control money but not majorities, they may layer new international institutions on top of the existing ones,³⁷ often through voluntary funding, hoping that those new institutions will be more performant. This only increases the complexity of global governance, does not improve the performance of existing institutions, and adds to policy accumulation and global governance complexity.

Thus, one should have expected UN80 to be a failure when it comes to cutting down on mandates. In the absence of such policy reductions, one would have predicted that mandates would be

increasingly thinned out or triaged by UN leadership as part of UN80.

Reforming the complex UN system and the joint decision-trap ('Workstream 3')

The same path-dependent forces that act at the individual agency level can also be found at the UN system level. The UN system can be described as a "global governance complex" understood as a "system of overlapping institutions and actors that govern a particular global policy issue".³⁸ Especially in times of polarization, when finding consensus or overcoming blocking minorities for reform is already hard in single institutions, reforming global governance complexes through complexity reduction should be less likely than simple "complexity management". Such complexity management is achieved by layering coordination bodies on top of or into the middle of governance complexes. Where costly coordination efforts do not find political or financial support, "low-cost institutions" in the form of new offices or committees that are easy to set up and maintain are created. They do not actually deliver better, they do not reach the same enforcement standards that established institutions are meant to deliver, and as cost-saving institutional solutions, they cannot reach the same scale for a meaningful

³⁷ Hanrieder, Tine. "Gradual change in international organisations: Agency theory and historical institutionalism." *Politics* 34, no. 4 (2014): 324-333.

³⁸ Eilstrup-Sangiovanni, Mette, and Oliver Westerwinter. "The global governance complexity

cube: Varieties of institutional complexity in global governance." *The Review of International Organizations* 17, no. 2 (2022): 233-262; p.234.

implementation that operational multilateral mandates can reach.³⁹ Thus, global governance complexes have the tendency to multiply their scale, and with each new institution or body created, the robustness of delivery declines while additional coordination costs are added through new bodies.

In this regard, the structural reform impetus of 'Workstream 3', especially the goal to merge UN entities with closely related mandates, seemed like an attempt to achieve simplification against the trend to make the system more complex. However, this attempt to overcome entity- and system-level complexity had all the features that are usually associated with the "joint decision trap"⁴⁰. Making those actors who would be directly affected by the reform decisions develop ideas and proposals – like the UN80 reform team's idea of creating reform clusters composed of agency heads that were asked to discuss the abolition or merging of their own agencies – could only result in failure.

The joint decision-trap is usually overcome with side payments, i.e., those who lose out in power through reform steps received additional funding over politically salient time horizons. However, in times of a UN financial crisis, as there is no excess funding available to offer such side payments, system reform becomes less likely. The budgetary crisis did not

act as a positive reform shock; it reduced the available resources that otherwise could have been used to shift compromise positions among multiple veto players. For example, promising additional AIDS funding while merging UNAIDS into the existing global health structures could have helped the defenders of UNAIDS' mandate to more easily agree to structural reform or merging, knowing that the policy goal they supported could be strengthened. Providing additional funding so that merging UN Women and UNFPA would lead to more resources for gender equality or better protection of sexual and reproductive rights would have eased discussion over this merger compared to discussions where institutions expected to lose out.

Finally, the joint decision-trap also relates to situations with extreme transaction costs, notably for understanding everyone's preferences over structural, legal, organizational, and policy impacts of UN system reform. This required an honest information broker with sufficient capacity to provide such information to assemblies, boards, ministers and reform coordinators. As providing such information is costly and time-consuming for a large system such as the UN, expecting systemic reform under time pressure and in a financial crisis was unlikely. Success was only expected for those parts of the system that were technically easy, with relatively simple interest constellations,

³⁹ Abbott, Kenneth W., and Benjamin Faude. "Choosing low-cost institutions in global governance." *International Theory* 13, no. 3 (2021): 397-426.

⁴⁰ Scharpf, Fritz W. "The joint-decision trap revisited." *JCMS: Journal of Common Market Studies* 44, no. 4 (2006): 845-864.

and low risk of alienating key member states or donors.

4. The UN80 initiative in the first half of 2025: From shock, to confusion, to a structured approach

In this section, the timeline frenzy of the early months of the UN80 process is traced across a number of key dates and dynamics, without capturing all aspects. What is most important to understand in retrospect is that, until the summer break of 2025, there was never a moment when the UN system seemed to have time to breathe, to reflect, to design a coherent reform process and systemic ideas where all actors would know what they were actually discussing for a longer time-horizon. Especially for outside observers and for UN staff around the world, this period of parallel massive staff and spending cuts and unpredictable reform steps meant huge uncertainty, anxiety, and pressure. Many messages received by the author

from UN staff until the autumn of 2025 were signals of related discontent and anxiety.

This feeling of disorder started when the Trump cuts hit the UN in January and February 2025, which put the wider UN system in a state of shock. Despite the predictability of what could happen – key funding scenarios for the case of a Trump reelection were out there by early 2025⁴¹ — it felt like the UN system was unprepared for the scale and speed of the cuts. Member states were informed by the UN Secretary-General of the grave liquidity crisis of the UN by letter on **7 February 2025**.⁴² However, despite a clear request of the SG to resolve the financial challenges, member states failed to agree on clear-cut measures before the summer break. In October 2025⁴³ and again in January 2026⁴⁴, Guterres issued repeated warnings of a potential insolvency of the organization.

The response from the UN's administrative leadership to move from initial shock to reform was much faster than the reaction of UN member states, which took until July 2025 to adopt their UN80 resolution.⁴⁵ This is in line with expectations from previous research on how UN agencies such as UNESCO

⁴¹ Baumann, Max-Otto; Sebastian Haug; and Marianne Beisheim. "Trump 2.0 and the United Nations." Friedrich Ebert Stiftung (FES). January 2025. <https://collections.fes.de/publikationen/ident/fes/21817>.

⁴² UN Secretary-General. "Letter to Member States on the Liquidity Crisis." 7 February 2025. Available via PassBlue: <https://www.passblue.com/wp-content/uploads/2025/02/Letter-SG-to-Member-State-Liquidity-Feb-2025.pdf>.

⁴³ United Nations. "United Nations Risks Bankruptcy as Resources Shrink, Needs Grow, Secretary-

General Warns Fifth Committee during Discussion on Proposed 2026 Programme Budget." UN Press Release GA/AB/4505, 17 October 2025.

<https://press.un.org/en/2025/gaab4505.doc.htm>.

⁴⁴ Patz, Ronny. LinkedIn post on the UN Secretary-General's letter to member states on the risk of bankruptcy in 2026. January 2028.

https://www.linkedin.com/posts/ronny-patz_un-secretarygeneral-germany-activity-7422914214727483392-G8lQ/.

⁴⁵ United Nations General Assembly. "UN80 Initiative", Resolution A/RES/79/318. <https://docs.un.org/en/A/RES/79/318>.

reacted to a budget shock, with the administrative reactions predating the intergovernmental reaction.⁴⁶

Already on **10 March 2025**, the UN's Emergency Relief Coordinator Tom Fletcher announced the "Humanitarian Reset", a reform of the humanitarian system in the face of massive budget cuts.⁴⁷ Two days later, on **12 March 2025**, UN Secretary-General Guterres publicly announced the UN80 process to the press. He informed that Under-Secretary-General Guy Ryder would lead the internal Task Force on UN80.⁴⁸ From there, it took four months, until **18 July 2025** for member states to endorse the initiative.⁴⁹ Member states were actually hesitant to follow the initiative for a resolution pushed for by the Russian Federation,⁵⁰ but Russia's aim was to maintain member state (= intergovernmental) control over the reform process and not leave it to the UN's administrative leadership to remain in the driver's seat. This is relevant because, by the time this resolution was adopted, key reform steps, including the work on a massive budget cut proposal and discussions on structural reforms of the UN system, had already started.

The core UN80 process has been managed by Under-Secretary-General Guy Ryder, a veteran high-level UN official who has already worked on reforming the International Labour Organization (ILO) in Geneva while he served as its Director-General a decade ago.⁵¹ He was supported by a team from high-level to junior UN officials. Among them, Jens Wandel was nominated Special Advisor on Reform already before the UN80 initiative started and got the additional title of "Adviser on the UN80 Initiative" at the **end of April 2025**.⁵²

Within the regular structures of the UN Secretariat, Under-Secretary-General for Management Catherine Pollard held together many aspects of the administrative and budgetary issues involved. The key actors involved in UN80 were all closely linked to Secretary-General Guterres and had already worked on reform efforts before. Guterres did not choose to go for an external reform group, not pushing for the nomination of a high-level panel. He rather went for an internal approach, repackaging existing reform streams and complementing them with a push for more system-wide efforts.

⁴⁶ Eckhard, Steffen, Ronny Patz, and Sylvia Schmidt. "Reform efforts, synchronization failure, and international bureaucracy: the case of the UNESCO budget crisis." *Journal of European Public Policy* 26, no. 11 (2019): 1639-1656.

⁴⁷ Inter-Agency Standing Committee (IASC). "Humanitarian Reset." <https://interagencystandingcommittee.org/humanitarian-reset>.

⁴⁸ United Nations. "Secretary-General's Press Encounter on the UN80 Initiative." 12 March 2025. <https://www.un.org/sg/en/content/sg/press-events/2025-03-12/secretary-generals-press-encounter-the-un80-initiative>.

⁴⁹ UNGA Resolution A/RES/79/318 of 18 July 2025 on the "UN80 Initiative".

⁵⁰ Russian Federation, UNGA draft resolution "UN80 Initiative", A/79/L.99 of 14 July 2025.

⁵¹ Genève internationale. "Interview with Guy Ryder, Director-General of the International Labour Organization." March 2015. <https://www.geneve-int.ch/node/4126>.

⁵² United Nations. "Mr. Jens Wandel of Denmark – Adviser to the UN80 Initiative." Personnel Appointment, 30 April 2025. <https://www.un.org/sg/en/content/sg/personnel-appointments/2025-04-30/mr-jens-wandel-of-denmark-adviser-the-un80-initiative>.

In this regard, UN80 started before it was announced. At the meeting of the High-level Committee on Management of the Chief Executives Board (CEB) of the UN system in October 2024, almost half a year before the announcement of UN80, the broad framework that guided UN80 was already clear:

“At the heart of the [October 2024] session was a half-day discussion on the growing complexities of funding in the United Nations system. The Committee examined how declining revenues, increasing demands and a shifting global financial climate have placed significant strain on United Nations system organizations.”⁵³

By the time the Chief Executives Board (CEB) administrative committee met in early **April 2025** in New York, the UN80 process had been announced and guided discussions. In a survey sent out across all UN agencies on **7 March**, days before UN80 was announced publicly, UN high-level managers had been asked to provide input on “proposals for far-reaching efficiency measures”. The result was a list of 108 potential measures, clustered by topic (payroll, HR, operations, procurement, supply chains) and into 22 distinct

initiatives⁵⁴. Through a survey, the CEB secretariat enquired which initiative would receive the highest support across the UN system and which initiatives were expected to result in the largest efficiencies.⁵⁵ Joint procurement appeared to be among the key priorities, but the survey showed that many UN agencies had already started most of the reform efforts, some more advanced across the UN system than others.

To increase the speed of debates, a strategic leak at the **end of April** of a document drafted by the UN80 Task Force around the Executive Office of the UN Secretary General indicated that wide-ranging reform ideas, including major mergers, were on the table.⁵⁶ In addition, Guterres’ *Chef de Cabinet* had asked all Secretariat departments to make proposals for potential relocations of services and other cost-saving measures in a letter sent out on **25 April 2025**.⁵⁷

All this happened shortly before, on **8-9 May 2025**, the UN System Chief Executives – the executive heads of UN agencies – met in Copenhagen, with an agenda segment called “*Adapting to new realities: leveraging the UN80 Initiative*”.⁵⁸ According to the meeting

⁵³ United Nations Chief Executives Board for Coordination (CEB). Report of the High-level Committee on Management at its forty-eighth session, 3-4 October 2024. CEB/2024/5. <https://docs.un.org/en/CEB/2024/5>.

⁵⁴ Contained in document CEB/2025/HLCM/14.

⁵⁵ Survey results contained in document CEB/2025/HLCM/2.

⁵⁶ United Nations (UN80 Task Force). "UN80 structural changes and programmatic realignment Compilation of non-attributable suggestions by the UN80 Task Force". April 2025. Leaked document published by Health Policy Watch. [https://healthpolicy-watch.news/wp-](https://healthpolicy-watch.news/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/Consolidated_ideas_realignments_restricted_2504081.pdf)

[content/uploads/2025/05/Consolidated_ideas_realignments_restricted_2504081.pdf](https://healthpolicy-watch.news/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/Consolidated_ideas_realignments_restricted_2504081.pdf).

⁵⁷ Executive Office of the Secretary-General (EOSG). "Chef de Cabinet Memo on Functional Review for Cost Reductions and Efficiencies." 25 April 2025. Available via Health Policy Watch at: https://healthpolicy-watch.news/wp-content/uploads/2025/05/EOSG-2025-02559_CdC-Memo-on-Functional-Review-for-Cost-Reductions-Efficiencies_SIGNED.pdf.

⁵⁸ United Nations Chief Executives Board for Coordination (CEB). First regular session of 2025 (Summary of deliberations). 8-9 May 2025.

summary, Guterres “*outlined a vision of a possibly smaller, but more coherent, efficient and effective United Nations, capable of delivering better results at less cost*”. He informed at that meeting about his approach to organize the generation of ideas for structural reforms through seven distinct clusters, which he would announce on **12 May 2025** to the wider public in a briefing.⁵⁹

However, by this time, the wide-reaching ideas were already on the table and the requests for efficiencies were already sent out. In the briefing, Guterres indicated the need for budget cuts, and at the **end of May** instructions were sent out for the preparation of revised estimates with 20% staff cuts,⁶⁰ indicating that Guterres was not willing to wait for reform discussions to progress in well-ordered sequencing before making budget cut proposals that would support, not preempt, reform discussions.

Despite the high speed and close sequence of actions, the choice of the seven reform clusters already revealed a lack of ambition in favor of realism: First, separating the development sector into two clusters, one inside the UN Secretariat and one for agencies funded by mostly voluntary contributions, suggested that Guterres was not actually looking for systemic

structural reforms but mainly feasible efficiency gains. Putting all Specialized Agencies, which are legally independent international organizations under the roof of the UN system, into their own cluster, indicated that Guterres had no ambition to address their huge diversity in mandates, sizes, and links to other UN agencies or ensure that duplication across the entire UN system would actually be addressed. More importantly, by keeping the reform clusters limited to UN agency leadership, Guterres showed that he had no interest in engaging with member states early on in what could become a legally and politically complicated dance of reforming the UN system.

On **24 June 2025**, the only public briefing of all seven reform clusters designated by the UN Secretary-General to develop ideas for structural reforms of the UN system (‘Workstream 3’) took place with member states in New York.⁶¹ By this time, the announcement of the UN80 initiative was three months old and each of the clusters had already organized quite a few meetings. Member states still had not positioned themselves vis-à-vis the UN80 reform while discussions among UN administrators continued. At the

<https://documents.un.org/doc/undoc/gen/n25/233/98/pdf/n2523398.pdf>.

⁵⁹ United Nations. “Secretary-General, Briefing on UN80 Initiative, Lays Out System-Wide Reform Plans to Make United Nations More Effective, Nimble, Fit for Today’s Challenges.” UN Press Release SG/SM/22644, 12 May 2025. <https://press.un.org/en/2025/sgsm22644.doc.htm>.

⁶⁰ Lederer, Edith M. “UN Seeks 20% Cut in Staff to Help Deal with a Funding Shortfall.” AP News, 31

May 2025. <https://apnews.com/article/un-budget-job-cuts-guterres-0e3e08fed833936fd41774ff9684cd85>.

⁶¹ United Nations (UN80 Initiative). “General Assembly 79th Session Clusters Update – UN80 Initiative.” (video recording). 24 June 2025.

<https://www.un.org/un80-initiative/en/general-assembly-79th-session-clusters-update-un80-initiative-24-june-2025>.

same time, the massive UN budget cuts were being prepared.

At townhall meetings with UN staff such as the one in Geneva on **5 June 2025**⁶², Guy Ryder and other UN officials tried to keep UN staff informed. Ryder also went to Vienna and intervened at meetings of UNESCO's Executive Board on **28 May** (via video),⁶³ at ILO Governing Body on **14 June**,⁶⁴ or at ITU Council on **19 June**⁶⁵. All of this showed a frenzy of parallel reform efforts, information meetings, collection of ideas from all corners of the UN system within just the first four months after the announcement of the UN80 reform process.

By **July 2025**, dozens of ideas were drafted, tabled, discussed, and criticized before the process slowly evolved into a more structured approach in which the three workstreams slowly gained their distinct procedural character. With the adoption of the UN General Assembly resolution on UN80 on **18 July 2025**, and with the presentation of the report of the Secretary-General on Mandate

Implementation ("Workstream 2") on **31 July 2025**,⁶⁶ it seemed as if member states realized just before the summer break that they also had to have a role in the process. On **2 September 2025**, they created the "Informal Ad Hoc Working Group" on the UN80 initiative, which was mainly tasked with following the mandate lifecycle review.⁶⁷ And by **7 November 2025**, Guterres finally presented an overall UN80 "Action Plan"⁶⁸ that put together all individual to-dos, some minor, some politically contentious, into a broader framework – although without a detailed timeline for individual actions or work pages.

The timeline above describes an extremely productive few months, generating many ideas and parallel dynamics. However, UN80 failed to synchronize administrative and (inter)governmental reform efforts, and the speed and breadth of initiatives overwhelmed many involved and affected. UN80 addressed the complexity of the entire UN system but did not shape a systemic process where ideas could evolve that

⁶² UNOG Staff Union. "Town Hall Meeting on UN80 with USG Guy Ryder." 3 June 2025. <https://unogstaffunion.org/townhall-meeting-on-un80-with-usg-guy-ryder-reunion-generale-sur-linitiative-un80-avec-le-secretaire-general-adjoint-guy-ryder/>.

⁶³ UNESCO. "Report by the Executive Board on its activities and programme implementation, Part I : Activities in 2024-2025, including its methods of work", 222 EX/22.I, 1 September 2025. <https://unesdoc.unesco.org/ark:/48223/pf0000395269>.

⁶⁴ International Labour Organization (ILO). "Governing Body 354th Session – Agenda (Revision 1)." GB.354/Agenda(Rev.1). 12 June 2025. <https://www.ilo.org/sites/default/files/2025-06/GB354-Agenda-Rev1-EN.pdf>.

⁶⁵ ITU Secretary-General and Co-coordinator of the UN80 Specialized Agencies Cluster, Statement by

Doreen Bogdan-Martin at the Informal meeting of the General Assembly (plenary) on the UN80 Initiative on 24 June 2025; https://estatemts.un.org/estatemts/10.0010/20250624150000000/GmxGmoGM/FkpQChxRdm_ny_c_en.PDF

⁶⁶ United Nations. "A mandate for change: UN releases proposals for streamlining of tasks as part of major reform agenda", Latest News. 1 August 2025. <https://www.ungeneva.org/en/news-media/news/2025/08/109128/mandate-change-un-releases-proposals-streamlining-tasks-part-major>.

⁶⁷ United Nations General Assembly. Decision 79/571. <https://igov.un.org/a/dec/79/571>.

⁶⁸ United Nations. "UN80 Initiative Action Plan." 7 November 2025. https://www.un.org/un80-initiative/sites/default/files/2025-11/UN80_Initiative_Action_Plan.pdf.

supported the alignment of money and majorities for systemic reform steps.

5. Assessing the three Workstreams of UN80

5.1 ‘Workstream 1’: Budget cuts with limited efficiency gains

Unlike the decades-long routine of adopting the UN budget around 23-24 December – with two major exceptions in 2020 and 2022 when negotiations dragged on until 30-31 December – the UN’s negotiations of the largest budget cuts in the history of the UN went until the last day of the year 2025.⁶⁹ Diplomats from many of the 193 countries spent their final week of the year scrambling in the basement of the iconic UN building complex by the East River, far removed from the global realities that their decisions would affect. They had to negotiate a complex package deal under extreme time pressure, with key documents delivered late, although everybody in New York knew since Spring 2025 that it would likely come to this situation.

On 30 December 2025, UN member states adopted a large budget cut that symbolized the first step of the so-called efficiency reforms under ‘Workstream 1’ of the UN80 reform process. On paper, the reduction from

\$3.72 billion adopted for the 2025 budget to the \$3.45 billion in the 2026 budget was smaller than what had been announced as a 15% budget cut. However, due to the UN’s Financial Regulations and Rules that were only partially revised by member states in December 2025, it was clear that UN cash flow in 2026 would be closer to the 15% cuts for which the UN Secretariat had planned. Because of the rules, member states would only have to pay around \$3.2 billion in assessed contributions for 2026.

Many public observers, and also the figures in the ACABQ report on the draft budget cuts (‘revised estimates’),⁷⁰ suggested that many of the proposed post cuts were for vacant positions. So, they were not, by and large, strategic efficiency cuts in line with UN80 reform ideas but rather budget cuts by attrition. This is in line with expectations from the broader literature on IO and UN reform that expect incremental, gradual change. Member states in the Fifth Committee spent significant time protecting their preferred pillar of the UN’s work (development, human rights, peace and security). This prevented significant shifts in the overall balance of the budget and direct formal cuts to already vacant positions.

The budget cut discussions also pretended that reductions could be implemented without affecting mandate delivery – while in reality policy triage

⁶⁹ Data on the routinization from 2005-2015 collected by Patz & Goetz (2019), see FN25; further data collected by the author through <https://research.un.org/c.php?g=137517&p=10727574>.

⁷⁰ United Nations General Assembly/ACABQ. “Tenth report of the Advisory Committee on Administrative and Budgetary Questions on the proposed programme budget for 2026”, A/80/7/Add.9., 26 November 2025. <https://docs.un.org/en/A/80/7/Add.9>.

was already happening. In a public briefing on the impact of the cutback on human rights work in Geneva, two perspectives became obvious: first, a cutback at the size of revised estimates *without* impact on mandate delivery is impossible. This showed that Workstreams 1 and 2 were not sufficiently connected. In addition, a lot of the UN80 reform impetus under Workstream 1 was driven by a logic that seemed to make sense in the UN headquarters in New York, while there was an impression of a disconnect from the reality in Geneva⁷¹. In a discussion in Vienna earlier in 2025, a UN Under-Secretary-General had also indicated that the UN Vienna perspective seemed to lack sufficient attention in New York.⁷² Decisions to relocate and centralize positions such as on payroll management to just a few global hubs (including Bangkok and Entebbe) reflected the efficiency agenda, while decisions to move selected positions in UN Women to Bonn were more indicative of catering to major contributor interests than based on the system-wide reflections that were still ongoing around Workstream 3.

⁷¹ UN Human Rights Council. "UNOG & OHCHR Chiefs Brief UN Member States on UN80 Impact on UN Human Rights Council & Architecture" (video), 5 November 2025. <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=ptedDTbsPEU>.

⁷² UNODA/VCDNP. "Enhancing the disarmament regime: a conversation with the UN USG and High Representative for Disarmament Affairs", 3 July 2025. <https://content.disarmamenteducation.org/videos/VCS-3-7-2025.mp4>.

5.2 Assessing 'Workstream 2': A creative process with unclear results

Unlike Workstream 1, which seemed obvious in times of scarce resources, and Workstream 3, for which early leaks had given a sense of direction, especially by focusing attention on potential mergers of UN entities, Workstream 2 remained rather elusive during the early months of UN80. Only when the Secretary-General presented his report on the mandate review⁷³ was there a sense of direction for these discussions. The report's main message was that the core UN system takes too many, too long, and under-resourced decisions, many of which receive little attention inside and outside the UN system.

Mapping the wider mandate landscape⁷⁴ as a starting point for trying to cut mushrooming mandates down to a more manageable amount seemed the initial main impetus of this workstream. However, the negative experience with a very similar mandate review initiated under Secretary-General Kofi Annan in the mid-2000s,⁷⁵ and the lack of appetite in many member states' New York missions to

⁷³ United Nations. "Mandate Implementation Review". Report of the Secretary General on Workstream 2 of the UN80 Initiative. September 2025. https://www.un.org/un80-initiative/sites/default/files/2025-09/2512998E_MIR_web.pdf.

⁷⁴ See at <https://mandates.un.org>.

⁷⁵ United Nations. "Mandating and delivering: analysis and recommendations to facilitate the review of mandates", Report of the Secretary General, 2006. <https://docs.un.org/en/A/60/733>.

go down this time-consuming road to (potentially) nowhere, meant that this goal was quickly capped. Instead of addressing policy or mandate accumulation to limit the need for increasing UN mandate triage, attention instead turned to the process of (new) mandate creation.

Maybe the most interesting aspect of this Workstream was the establishment of the informal ad hoc working group (IAHWG) led by the Permanent Representatives of Jamaica (“Global South” from the north) and New Zealand (“Global North” from the south). Between the creation of the group in September 2025 and the end of the year, the two ambassadors organized a “discovery phase” around a range of briefings followed by member-state-driven discussions on the three stages of the mandate lifecycle. Especially the early and late discussions in the Working Group showed a remarkable level of openness of minds, with participation at a high diplomatic level and often frank

interventions on past and present experiences.

At the time of writing, the intermediate report of the co-chairs of the informal ad hoc working group (IAHWG) on what they called the ‘discovery phase’ has been published⁷⁶ and discussed by member states. Based on feedback received from member states⁷⁷, on input from academia and think tanks⁷⁸, and from NGOs and civil society⁷⁹, this intermediate report set out rather abstract findings which were discussed in January 2026,⁸⁰ alongside the zero-draft resolution dated 8 January 2026.⁸¹

The limited ambition when it comes to the review of existing mandates was confirmed as this part of the reform would be postponed until “the end of GA82”, which is UN-language for mid-2028, when the 82nd General Assembly will end. Policy accumulation wins. Whether member states will have the appetite to review the landscape of mandates across the UN system after they have already spent two years discussing money, mergers, and

⁷⁶ United Nations (Informal Ad Hoc Working Group). " Interim Report back by the Co-Chairs of the Informal Ad Hoc Working Group on the Mandate Implementation Review." 11 December 2025. <https://www.un.org/un80-initiative/sites/default/files/2025-12/IAHWG%20Interim%20Report%20-%2011%20December.pdf..>

⁷⁷ Some selected statements and input are collected here: <https://www.un.org/un80-initiative/en/informal-ad-hoc-working-group-member-state-inputs>

⁷⁸ Center on International Cooperation (NYU). " Consultation on Mandate Review. Key Takeaways for Co-Chairs." 24 November 2025. <https://www.un.org/un80-initiative/sites/default/files/2025-12/20251124%20->

[UN80%20Consultation%20on%20Mandate%20Strengthening.pdf](https://www.un.org/un80-initiative/sites/default/files/2025-12/UN80%20Consultation%20on%20Mandate%20Strengthening.pdf).

⁷⁹ Coalition For The UN We Need. " Consulting Civil Society: CSO Inputs to the Informal Ad-Hoc Working Group on the UN80 Initiative." December 2025. <https://www.un.org/un80-initiative/sites/default/files/2025-12/UN80%20Initiative%20CSO%20Report.pdf>

⁸⁰ UN WebTV. "Informal Ad hoc Working Group on UN80 initiative - General Assembly, 80th session" (video), Briefing, 8 January 2026. <https://webtv.un.org/en/asset/k15/k1539zqxls>.

⁸¹ United Nations. "Mandate Creation, Implementation and Review for an Effective United Nations", IAHWG zero draft. 8 January 2026. https://www.un.org/un80-initiative/sites/default/files/2026-01/260108%20IAHWG%20zero%20draft_0.pdf.

mandates as part of Workstream 3 will be questionable.

Maybe the most substantive zero draft paragraph was one most closely linked to the systemic dimensions of governance of the UN system (highlighted by the author):

*“3. Requests the Presidents of the General Assembly, ECOSOC, and the Security Council in consultation with the Secretary-General and the wider United Nations system to undertake a **review of existing intergovernmental coordination and oversight mechanisms** to develop recommendations on possible improvements to avoid duplication, and harmonize and enhance delivery of mandates, to be provided to Member States as soon as practicable and in any event by 31 December 2026 for their consideration”*

This indicates the growing realization that mandate duplication across the wider UN system will not be solved in the UN General Assembly.

While the mandate registry created for this workstream may provide member states a source for understanding some of the duplication in the core UN system, duplication in the domains of health, human rights, gender, development or peace and humanitarian affairs will only be addressed when they are discovered at system level and addressed at system level. Nevertheless, the limited ambition of Workstream 2 to reduce

existing mandates raises questions about whether mandate accumulation will ever be addressed or whether mandate thinning out, mandate triage, and mandate reprioritization will mainly be addressed by (lack of) core and voluntary funding.

5.3 Assessing ‘Workstream 3’: A long to-do list, with more action than plan

By early 2026, the structural reform impetus of ‘Workstream 3’ – simplifying and streamlining the UN system through mergers and joint services – was the least advanced but most discussed of the three streams, at least outside of public debates on cost-cutting. The early leak of potential mergers (UNHCR-IOM; UN Women-UNFPA; UNDP-UNOPS, etc.) at the end of April catapulted these debates high onto the public stage. Those merger discussions became part of the seven thematic clusters that Guterres had set up in May 2025 and that were supposed to bring in ideas for structural reform and efficiencies.

However, informal feedback from these discussions indicated that the joint decision-trap had hit those meetings: with agency heads or their deputies and other focal points representing “their” agency or departments in those discussions, cluster debates were far from the creative process of the Workstream 2 discovery phase. Instead, defending each agency’s turf became more important than developing genuine system-wide

reform ideas. At the June 2025 public briefing by the respective cluster leads, it was also clear that some clusters were much more advanced than others by this time. Especially the “Humanitarian Reset” reflections, which had started alongside the UN80 process, seemed to be most advanced, likely because the massive funding cuts had hit the UN agencies involved in the delivery of humanitarian aid most forcefully.

Thus, when Guterres presented his *Workstream 3* report in September 2025,⁸² the proposals contained therein seemed much less ambitious compared to what had been leaked in April. The pull towards the *status quo* and gradual reform steps at the system level seemed strong. The legal and political difficulties of even approaching mergers such as UNHCR and IOM, the latter being an independent international organization, seemed to be so hard that only mergers that were under the purview of the General Assembly, ECOSOC, or agency boards such as UN Women-UNFPA and UNOPS-UNDP remained on the agenda. A few further sunseting proposals (UNAIDS) and agency incorporations (e.g. UNSSC into UNITAR) also remained on the table. However, these discussions were only really beginning in the boards and ad hoc committees formed at the inter-agency level by early 2026, so that the outcome of these discussions is unclear at the time of writing. Especially where

member states feared that mergers could actually undermine mandates that they liked, political considerations against mergers trumped minor efficiency gains. Chances are that no major mergers will happen or that superficial and low-cost shifts in coordination will be sold as major successes before the end of Guterres’ second term.

In the Workstream 3 report, translated into the UN80 Action Plan published in November 2025, most of what had been merger discussions before turned into requests for clarification:

“Clarify roles to reduce duplication and strengthen impact 32. *Programmatic overlaps in food, mobility, data, health and nutrition reduce efficiency. Agencies are aligning responsibilities: FAO/WFP/IFAD on food security; UNHCR/IOM on mobility; UNICEF/WFP/UNHCR on beneficiary data; WHO/UNICEF/WFP on health and nutrition. Clearer divisions of labour will mean greater efficiency, predictability and results at scale.*” (Workstream 3 report, p.18)

What is noteworthy in this paragraph is the inclusion of two UN Specialized Agencies – FAO and WHO – over which the UN Secretary-General has limited to no formal authority. These limits became more obvious when the

⁸² United Nations. “Shifting Paradigms: United to Deliver. Report of the Secretary-General on Workstream 3. Changing Structures and Realigning Programmes”, September 2025.

https://www.un.org/un80-initiative/sites/default/files/2025-09/UN80_WS3-1_250918_1901.pdf.

Directors-General of WHO and FAO signaled in autumn 2025 that they preferred their own reform processes. In the WHO, the reform of a global health architecture was put onto the agenda in December 2025 alongside UN80,⁸³ while FAO's Director-General suggested that his own reform ideas were much more advanced but had been rejected by a group of FAO member states.⁸⁴ Other Directors-General, such as at UNIDO, indicated that they already had reformed in the past,⁸⁵ suggesting less willingness to engage with the UN80 process, while member states clarified that engaging with reform efforts for the UN at country level should remain a priority for all agencies.⁸⁶

Country-level discussions seemed to be a key part of UN reform debates at member state level, especially where major donors who fund the UN's operational system⁸⁷ were concerned. However, since country-level operations are largely dependent on

voluntary funding, this ultimately depends more on donor than on agency decisions.

Overall, Workstream 3 started as the most far-reaching possibility for reforming the global governance complex(es) of the UN system, but it faced the expected resistance from agencies, from member states fearing to lose their fiefdoms, from partners and lobby groups who feared their preferred interlocutors would lose out, or simply because legal constraints could only be overcome if there was consensus among all member states. The discussions on this workstream were productive because many actors involved for the first time were forced to confront some of these realities head-on. However, more forceful proposals, such as a "new UN system-wide budgetary coordination process"⁸⁸ that would address the fragmentation of the system by pushing more coherence for funding decisions across policies, agencies, and levels of the system,

⁸³ World Health Organization (WHO). "Reform of the Global Health Architecture and the UN80 Initiative." Executive Board, 158th Session, Document EB158/44, 22 December 2025.

https://apps.who.int/gb/ebwha/pdf_files/EB158/B158_44-en.pdf.

⁸⁴ Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). "Director-General Speech: Joint Meeting of the Programme and Finance Committees – Opening Statement by DG Qu Dongyu." <https://www.fao.org/director-general/speeches/details/joint-meeting-of-the-programme-and-finance-committeesopening-statement/en>.

⁸⁵ United Nations Industrial Development Organization (UNIDO). "Statement by the Director-General." 26 May 2025. <https://www.unido.org/news/statement-director-general>.

⁸⁶ European Union (EEAS). "EU Statement – General Debate, 21st Session UNIDO General

Conference." 23 November 2025.

https://www.eeas.europa.eu/delegations/vienna-international-organisations/eu-statement-general-debate-21st-session-unido-general-conference-23-november-2025_en.

⁸⁷ Federal Department of Foreign Affairs of Switzerland. "Understanding the UN. The UN at Country Level

A practical guide to the United Nations Operational System."

<https://www.understandingtheun.org/document s/UN-Country-Level-handbook.pdf>.

⁸⁸ Patz, Ronny (2025). "Reforming the UN During a Financial Crisis: A Foreseeable Failure to Align Money, Mandates and Majorities." Global Governance Institute. <https://www.globalgovernance.eu/publications/reforming-the-un-during-a-financial-crisis-a-foreseeable-failure-to-align-money-mandates-and-majorities>.

never even made it onto the Workstream 3 agenda.

6. UN80 and the ignorance of geopolitical disruptions

“The Secretary-General presented an overview of the state of the world, reflecting on the current geopolitical landscape and the multiple crises facing the international community and the United Nations system, notably the funding crisis and major challenges to the rules-based international order, deepening global divides and tensions, the growing complexity of conflicts, climate change and unregulated digital technologies.”

(CEB meeting summary, 8-9 May 2025, p.1⁸⁹)

There are various ways of thinking about the ongoing UN80 initiative and any future UN reform efforts. There are those who might say that UN80 did

what was possible and Guterres proposed what he and his team thought were feasible reform efforts, some of which might even allow cutting costs and reducing the footprint of the UN where not absolutely necessary.

However, there are those who underlined that UN80 has been a largely administrative exercise, overly focused on cutting corners, but with little high-level geopolitical involvement.⁹⁰ At best, UN80 was a response to the political shifts in the USA and in major Western donor countries, which had either been alienated from the UN or whose national budgets shifted towards military expenditure and away from multilateral aid for humanitarian and development.

Trump’s unilateral interventions in Venezuela, his “neo-royal”⁹¹ approach to the Peace Board that turned from an instrument for Gaza to a competitor of the UN Security Council, and the withdrawal from WHO, UNESCO and many other UN agencies⁹² alongside the US’ refusal to pay for assessed contributions for the regular and peacekeeping budgets for 2024 and 2025 all indicated that the disruptions

⁸⁹ United Nations Chief Executives Board for Coordination (CEB). First regular session of 2025 (Summary of deliberations). 8-9 May 2025. <https://docs.un.org/en/CEB/2025/1>.

⁹⁰ Camelli, Thibault and Fernando Marani. "Why Member State Engagement Needs to Be at the Heart of UN80 to Unlock Its Success." Center on International Cooperation (CIC), NYU. October 2025. <https://cic.nyu.edu/resources/why-member-state-engagement-needs-to-be-at-the-heart-of-un80-to-unlock-its-success/>.

⁹¹ The New York Times. "'Neo-Royalism' and what it says about Trump", 4 February 2026.

<https://www.nytimes.com/2026/02/04/business/economy/trump-history-newroyalism.html>.

⁹² The White House. "Withdrawing the United States from International Organizations, Conventions and Treaties That Are Contrary to the Interests of the United States." Presidential Action, 7 January 2026.

<https://www.whitehouse.gov/presidential-actions/2026/01/withdrawing-the-united-states-from-international-organizations-conventions-and-treaties-that-are-contrary-to-the-interests-of-the-united-states/>.

were more than just a discontent about efficiency and effectiveness of the UN that could be addressed by gradual organizational and systemic reforms.

In December 2025, the Chinese government announced the creation of the “*Group of Friends of Global Governance*” with more than 40 member states.⁹³ This was announced by China during the 11 December meeting of the UN80 working group and signaled that China was willing to push for reforms well beyond the bureaucratic list of proposals contained in the UN80 Action Plan. China’s share of the regular UN budget has risen to 20% since 2025, which makes it by far the largest assessed contributor to the regular budgets of all Specialized Agencies that the USA is leaving or not paying to. This financial responsibility makes China more budget-conscious, arguing for UN budget discipline and a reduction of UN bureaucracy in many public meetings. It also continued its practice to pay late for the UN budget. Its last tranche for the 2025 budget was only paid on 29 October 2025.⁹⁴ This was earlier than the last tranche for the 2024 UN budget on 27 December 2024, but still very late in the year.⁹⁵

The EU and its member states, as the largest bloc of donor countries, were maybe the group of countries most focused on efficiency gains through UN80, but at the same time focused on the Russian War in Ukraine much more than on aid delivery. The G77 as a substantive negotiating bloc in UN budget discussions⁹⁶ did not formulate a coherent vision around UN80, but it was clear that any of the cost-cutting attempts that would weaken UN presence and structures in Africa, Asia, or Latin America were unwelcome. Some of the minor and middle powers such as Singapore and Switzerland, the latter not without self-interest for protecting their international Geneva, were actively involved in reform discussions, but especially in early 2026 it became clear in various speeches that, at political level, concerns were rather about a new world order where Great Powers would not care for international institutions and the interests of smaller powers than about limited reform efforts in New York, Geneva or Nairobi.

At no stage in the process did the Secretary-General switch from a project-management and administrative approach for UN80 to a more geopolitical moment where he

⁹³ Permanent Mission of China to the UN. "Joint Statement on the Launch of the Group of Friends of Global Governance." 9 December 2025. https://un.china-mission.gov.cn/eng/czthd/202512/t20251210_11769936.htm.

⁹⁴ United Nations. Contributions received for 2025 for the United Nations Regular Budget. https://www.un.org/en/ga/contributions/honourroll_2025.shtml.

⁹⁵ United Nations. Contributions received for 2024 for the United Nations Regular Budget.

https://www.un.org/en/ga/contributions/honourroll_2024.shtml.

⁹⁶ Baumann, Max-Otto; Anna Novoselova; Javier Surasky; and Philipp Schönrock. "The Group of 77 and Global Dialogue in the United Nations General Assembly." German Institute of Development and Sustainability (IDOS) Discussion Paper 13/2024. https://www.idos-research.de/fileadmin/user_upload/pdfs/publikationen/discussion_paper/2024/DP_13.2024.pdf.

publicly asked the question whether what was on the table would be enough to save the UN through this moment of disruption. What is a more effective and efficient UN system when there are fundamental differences in views on what the system should deliver? What if some actors actively undermine the functioning of the system at such a level that smaller reform initiatives are dwarfed? Why did the Secretary-General not address questions of governance that would be required to bring together the fragmented geopolitical landscape of member states and donors, instead of keeping diplomats, bureaucrats and a few politicians busy with minor questions of the functioning of a system that was largely driven by a few major donors of earmarked funding?

UN80 never tried to give answers to these questions. Thus, even where the process may be a productive success and not just a productive failure, it currently raises more questions than it answers. Whether those questions and answers will be addressed in 2026 and beyond remains to be seen.

7. Short conclusions and outlook beyond 2026

In 2025, the UN80 Initiative has triggered large-scale reform discussions, often starting from ambitious ideas that mostly returned to superficial, technocratic, or gradual organizational and procedural changes.

The mandate accumulation has not been stopped or even reduced, only a limited number of mergers are still discussed, and no better governance has been introduced. In this regard, this contribution has framed the process as a productive failure in a year with one of the largest financial and staff contractions in the UN system's history.

In 2026, the UN80 Initiative and further resource cuts will likely continue to shake up the UN system. The difference to 2025 will be that the overall UN system will have 20-30 percent less staff and capacity to absorb any additional shocks, any new ideas, and any proposals that require political, diplomatic, and administrative energy to develop and implement. It is likely that, beyond a few core aspects of UN80 that are just technocratically easy and necessary, the reform fatigue will set in, and the political focus could shift more to the election of a new UN Secretary-General (and other executive leaders such as the WHO Director-General) than to organizational and systemic reform.

Throughout 2026, there will also be more and more data about the state of the UN system in 2025, following the first avalanche of staff cuts. Many reform steps in 2025 were initiated in 'blind flight', as indicated in the ad hoc creation of new mandate registries that did not exist before. This is important because there is a danger that continuing reform discussions are actually reflections on a UN system that no longer exists and that may not return to its old size given the current geopolitical disruptions and budgetary discussions in key member states.

By autumn of 2026, before the new Secretary-General comes into office,

the current SG and member states will need to take stock of what has been achieved and what they want to continue to work on going into 2026-27. The question is whether the geopolitical disruptions will add a high-level political dimension to these discussions or whether this will remain the domain of working-level UN experts and diplomats, maintaining momentum for any administrative reform steps that may save a few million US-Dollars here and there and cut staff in a system that will increasingly rely on consultants and other non-regular staff to deliver on the same amount of mandates under conditions of significantly reduced resources, somewhere between mandate triage and ever thinner mandate delivery. UN80 may have been a productive failure, but the question is how to prevent that failure, and race to the lowest common denominator does not end in a fully dysfunctional UN system.

8. Recommendations

The following recommendations build on the discussions above and address different actors willing and able to deliver intellectual or governance input into UN80 and the geopolitical disruptions moving forward. These recommendations are explicitly not about any specific reform proposal but rather a reflection on the procedural and substantive shortcomings observed throughout the UN80 process. The main policy recommendation remains a new centralized process of resource coordination, something akin to integrated budgeting at the UN level, where money and geopolitics become

more aligned than they are today. The following recommendations are much less ambitious but actually feasible for the actors to whom they are addressed.

A. Recommendations to the academic and policy community

Recommendation A.1 The UN80 process has shown that few actors have a big picture view of the entire UN system, its agencies, structures, mandates, and finances. In the next five years, there should be a **concerted research effort to understand the landscape of all UN entities**, the links and overlaps between their respective mandates, and the wider UN system administrative structures that sustain them.

Recommendation A.2 In 2026, member states and donors have been slow to develop ideas for a strategic coordination of UN80 reforms, especially with a view to achieving agreement across geopolitical dividing lines. The research and policy community should not waste time developing new reform ideas – very little of what was proposed in 2025 was new – but rather **develop ideas for realistic pathways to existing reform options**. The goal would be to show gradual or disruptive pathways that (could) fit the diverse geopolitical and bureaucratic interests of actors that hold veto-power, including by considering side-payments and package deals.

B. Recommendations to governments (as UN members and donors)

Recommendation B.1 Governments have failed to govern the UN80 reform process in 2025, leaving the majority of key decisions to 2026 and beyond. In 2026, **individual governments and groups of governments should provide high-level guidance**, including from foreign ministers or heads of state and government, on their preferred outcomes for the UN system heading into the 2030s. Flexible coalition building should be prioritized over established blocs since many reform options have support across blocs even when intra-bloc consensus is missing.

Recommendation B.2 Key donor governments should agree to **support backbone and core multilateral structures** of the UN system instead of financing earmarked pet projects and using the UN as mere implementing agencies. Pooled funding mechanisms should only be used to **link voluntary funding back to collectively agreed priorities** and mandates, especially where those mandates have strong multilateral backing close to consensus.

C. Recommendations to UN executive managers

Recommendation C.1 The UN80 reform process in 2025 has shown that structural reforms and financial crisis management are difficult to combine. **UN managers should leave the key**

reform efforts to member states and instead **focus on stabilizing the remaining UN system within the reduced resource base**, including by making targeted recommendations to donors on how to (re) allocate limited resources individually and collectively. Resource mobilization should be focused at the global level or coordinated through Country Teams to ensure agency-level coherence in line with global reform goals and country-level coherence in line with nationally agreed priorities.

Recommendation C.2 In 2025, while the UN humanitarian system was able to demonstrate its ability to increase coordination under conditions of massive resource cuts, other parts of the UN system (including in the reform clusters) did not appear willing to accept the need for increased coordination. In 2026-27, **the UN's Chief Executives Board (CEB) should gain an increasingly prominent role** in shaping cross-system coordination, using the impetus of a new Secretary-General to find new compromises linked to the current geopolitical landscape, and link UN reform efforts with key government initiatives at the highest possible level(s) to ensure reforms have the necessary backing before being implemented.

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